

Quiz on transformers and stable diffusion

March 19, 2025

General information

- The quiz lasts for 45 minutes.
- No additional material is allowed.
- Mark your answers only in the answer sheet.
- At the end, you only hand in the answer sheet. You can keep the other sheets.
- Mark the correct answer in the answer sheet using whichever mark you prefer. The quiz is graded manually.
- If you want to change answers, indicate that clearly in the answer sheet. In case of ambiguities, the interpretation of the grading TA is final.

1. Transformer-diagram Sudoku

Figure 1 shows the architecture of a transformer, with some of its components covered.

Figure 1: The transformer architecture

- (a) (1 point) Which component is covered by Γ ?
 - A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A multi-headed cross-attention mechanism.
 - D. A multi-headed masked cross-attention mechanism.
- (b) (1 point) Which component is covered by Δ ?
 - A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A multi-headed cross-attention mechanism.
 - D. A multi-headed masked cross-attention mechanism.
- (c) (1 point) Which component is covered by Ω ?
 - A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A multi-headed cross-attention mechanism.
 - D. A multi-headed masked cross-attention mechanism.

2. Attention mechanism

We give here an incomplete implementation of a multi-headed self-attention mechanism.

```
1 class MultiHeadedSelfAttention(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, input_dim, key_dim, val_dim, num_heads=1):
3         """
4         Args:
5         input_dim: Dimensionality of input embeddings.
6         hidden_dim: Dimensionality of key, query, and value vectors.
7         num_heads: Number of attention heads.
8         """
9         super(MultiHeadedSelfAttention, self).__init__()
10        self.num_heads = num_heads
11        self.key_dim = key_dim
12        self.val_dim = val_dim
13
14        self.WQ = nn.Linear(input_dim, key_dim * num_heads, bias=False)
15        self.WK = nn.Linear(input_dim, key_dim * num_heads, bias=False)
16        self.WV = nn.Linear(input_dim, val_dim * num_heads, bias=False)
17        self.WA = nn.Linear(val_dim * num_heads, input_dim)
18
19    def forward(self, E):
20        Q = self.WQ(E) # (B, N, num_heads * key_dim)
21        K = self.WK(E) # (B, N, num_heads * key_dim)
22        V = self.WV(E) # (B, N, num_heads * val_dim)
23
24        # Rearrange for multi-head attention (B, num_heads, N, (key/val
25        #   )_dim)
26        Q = rearrange(Q, 'B N (H D) -> B H N D', H=self.num_heads, D=
27        self.key_dim)
28        K = rearrange(K, 'B N (H D) -> B H N D', H=self.num_heads, D=
29        self.key_dim)
30        V = rearrange(V, 'B N (H D) -> B H N D', H=self.num_heads, D=
31        self.val_dim)
32
33        P = _____
34        S = _____
35
36        A = _____
37        A = _____
38
39        return self.WA(A)
```

(a) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 29?

- A. `P = torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bmnd", Q, K)`
- B. `P = torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bmn", Q, K)`
- C. `P = torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bhmnd", Q, K)`
- D. `P = torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bhmn", Q, K)`
- E. `P = torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bhmn", Q, K)`

- (b) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 30?
- A. `F.softmax(P / math.sqrt(self.key_dim))`
 - B. `F.softmax(P / math.sqrt(self.key_dim), dim=-1)`
 - C. `F.softmax(P / math.sqrt(self.val_dim), dim=-1)`
 - D. `F.softmax(P / math.sqrt(self.val_dim))`
 - E. `F.softmax(P / math.sqrt(self.val_dim), dim=-2)`
- (c) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 32?
- A. `torch.einsum("bhmn,bhnd->bdmn", V, S)`
 - B. `torch.einsum("bhmd,bhmn->bhmd", V, S)`
 - C. `torch.einsum("bhnd,bhmn->bhmd", V, S)`
 - D. `torch.einsum("bhmd,bhnd->bmnd", V, S)`
- (d) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 33?
- A. `rearrange(A, 'B H M N->(B H) N M', H=self.num_heads, M=A.shape[-1])`
 - B. `rearrange(A, 'B H N D->B (H N) D', H=self.num_heads, N=A.shape[2])`
 - C. `rearrange(A, 'B H M D->B D (H M)', H=self.num_heads, M=A.shape[2])`
 - D. `rearrange(A, 'B H N D->B N (H D)', H=self.num_heads, D=self.val_dim)`

3. Diffusion process

Consider the following incomplete implementation of a diffusion process that we use for an implementation of stable diffusion.

```

1 class DiffusionModel(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, model, device, T=1000, beta_start=1e-4, beta_end
      =0.02):
3         super(DiffusionModel, self).__init__()
4         self.model = model
5         self.T = T
6         self.device = device
7         with torch.no_grad():
8             self.betas = torch.linspace(beta_start, beta_end, T).to(
              device)
9             self.alphas = 1 - self.betas
10            self.alphas.to(device)
11            self.alpha_bars = torch.cumprod(self.alphas, dim=0).to(
              device)
12
13    def forward_diffusion(self, x0, t):
14        """
15        Forward process:  $q(x_t | x_0)$ 
16        Add noise to the input image  $x_0$  at time step  $t$ .
17        """
18        noise = torch.randn_like(x0).to(self.device)
19        alpha_bar_t = self.alpha_bars[t].to(self.device)
20        noisy_x = _____
21        return noisy_x, noise

```

```

22
23     def reverse_process(self, xt, txt_emb, t):
24         """
25         Reverse process:  $p(x_{t-1} | x_t)$ 
26         Predict the noise and denoise the image.
27         """
28         predicted_noise = self.model(x=xt, txt_emb=txt_emb, t=t)
29         alpha_t = self.alphas[t].to(self.device)
30         alpha_bar_t = self.alpha_bars[t].to(self.device)
31         scaling_factor = (1 - alpha_t) / torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t)
32         xt_prev = _____
33
34         return xt_prev

```

(a) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 20?

- A. `noisy_x = torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t) * x0 + torch.sqrt(alpha_bar_t) * noise`
- B. `noisy_x = torch.sqrt(alpha_bar_t) * x0 + torch.sqrt(alpha_bar_t) * noise`
- C. `noisy_x = x0 + torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t) * noise`
- D. `noisy_x = torch.sqrt(alpha_bar_t) * x0 + torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t) * noise`
- E. `noisy_x = torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t) * x0 + torch.sqrt(1 - alpha_bar_t) * noise`

(b) (1 point) The `reverse_process` method implements an improved version of the classic reverse process for a diffusion process. Which code should go in Line 32?

- A. `xt - predicted_noise`
- B. `xt + scaling_factor * predicted_noise`
- C. `(xt - scaling_factor * predicted_noise) / torch.sqrt(alpha_t)`
- D. `torch.sqrt(xt + scaling_factor * predicted_noise) / torch.sqrt(alpha_t)`
- E. `torch.sqrt(xt - predicted_noise) / torch.sqrt(alpha_t)`

4. (1 point) **Positional encoding**

Identify the correct positional encoding matrix from the following images. The number of rows is the number of possible positions and the number of columns is the number of dimensions in the embedding space.

A. _____

B. _____

C. _____

D. _____

5. **Cross-attention** We give here an incomplete implementation of a cross-attention mechanism for UNets.

```
1   class MyCrossAttention(nn.Module):
2
3   def __init__(self, img_channels, emb_dim, key_dim, val_dim, out_dim
4       , num_heads):
5       super(MyCrossAttention, self).__init__()
6       self.key_dim = key_dim // num_heads
7       self.val_dim = val_dim // num_heads
8       self.emb_dim = emb_dim
9       self.num_heads = num_heads
10      self.img_channels = img_channels
11      self.out_dim = out_dim
12
13      self.WQ = nn.Conv2d(self.img_channels, self.key_dim*self.
14          num_heads, kernel_size=3, stride=1, padding=1)
15      self.WK = nn.Linear(self.emb_dim, self.key_dim*self.num_heads)
16      self.WV = nn.Linear(self.emb_dim, self.val_dim*self.num_heads)
17
18      self.WA = nn.Conv2d(self.val_dim * self.num_heads, self.out_dim
19          , kernel_size=3, stride=1, padding=1)
20
21  def forward(self, E, textE):
22      Q = self.WQ(E)
23      K = _____
24      V = _____
25
26      Q = rearrange(Q, 'B (F D) H W -> B F D H W', F=self.num_heads,
27          D=self.key_dim)
28      K = _____
29      V = _____
30
31      P = torch.einsum(_____)
32      S = F.softmax(_____)
33
34      A = torch.einsum(_____)
35      A = rearrange(_____)
36      out = self.WA(A)
37      return out
```

- (a) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 20?

- A. `K = self.WK(E)`
- B. `K = self.WV(E)`
- C. `K = self.WK(textE)`
- D. `K = self.WV(textE)`

- (b) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 21?

- A. `V = self.WK(E)`
- B. `V = self.WV(E)`

- C. `V = self.WK(textE)`
 D. `V = self.WV(textE)`
- (c) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 24?
- A. `K = rearrange(K, 'B M (F D) -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, D=self.key_dim)`
 B. `K = rearrange(K, 'B M (F D) -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, D=self.val_dim)`
 C. `K = rearrange(K, 'B (M F) D -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, M=K.shape[1] // self.num_heads)`
 D. `K = rearrange(K, 'B (M F) D -> B F D M', F=self.num_heads, M=K.shape[1] // self.num_heads)`
- (d) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 25?
- A. `V = rearrange(V, 'B M (F D) -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, D=self.key_dim)`
 B. `V = rearrange(V, 'B M (F D) -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, D=self.val_dim)`
 C. `V = rearrange(V, 'B (M F) D -> B F M D', F=self.num_heads, M=K.shape[1] // self.num_heads)`
 D. `V = rearrange(V, 'B (M F) D -> B F D M', F=self.num_heads, M=K.shape[1] // self.num_heads)`
- (e) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 27?
- A. `P = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfdm->bmdhw", Q, K)`
 B. `P = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfmd->bmdhw", Q, K)`
 C. `P = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfdm->bfmhw", Q, K)`
 D. `P = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfdm->bfmhw", Q, K)`
- (f) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 28?
- A. `S = F.softmax(P / (self.key_dim ** 0.5), dim=1)`
 B. `S = F.softmax(P / (self.key_dim ** 0.5), dim=2)`
 C. `S = F.softmax(P / (self.key_dim ** 0.5), dim=3)`
 D. `S = F.softmax(P / (self.key_dim ** 0.5), dim=4)`
- (g) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 30?
- A. `A = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfdm->bfhwm", S, V)`
 B. `A = torch.einsum("bfmhw,bfdm->bfhwm", S, V)`
 C. `A = torch.einsum("bfdhw,bfmd->bfmhw", S, V)`
 D. `A = torch.einsum("bfmhw,bfmd->bfdhw", S, V)`

6. Denoising UNet

Below is a partial implementation of a UNet for a diffusion process.

```
1 class MyMiniUNet(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, device, dim_txt_emb, T, max_sentence_len=16)
3         :
4         super(MyMiniUNet, self).__init__()
5
6         self.enc1 = TempConvBlock(device=device, T=T, in_channels
7             =1, out_channels=4)
8         self.enc2 = ConvBlock(in_channels=4, out_channels=8)
9
10        self.pool = nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2)
11
12
13        self.center = TempConvBlock(device=device, T=T, in_channels
14            =8, out_channels=16)
15        self.xatt = _____
16
17
18        self.up2 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(16,8,kernel_size=2,stride=2)
19        self.dec2 = _____
20        self.up1 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(8,4,kernel_size=2,stride=2)
21        self.dec1 = TempConvBlock(device=device, T=T, in_channels
22            =8, out_channels=4)
23
24        self.final = nn.Conv2d(4, 1, kernel_size=1)
25
26        self.pe = MyPositionalEncoding(dim_txt_emb,
27            max_sentence_len, device=device).pe.unsqueeze(0)
28
29
30    def forward(self, x, txt_emb, t):
31        pe = self.pe[:, :txt_emb.shape[1], :]
32        txt_emb += pe
33
34        enc1 = self.enc1(x, t)
35        enc2 = self.enc2(self.pool(enc1))
36
37        center = self.center(self.pool(enc2), t)
38        center = self.xatt(center, txt_emb)
39
40        dec2 = self.dec2(torch.cat([self.up2(center), enc2], dim=1)
41            )
42        dec1 = self.dec1(torch.cat([self.up1(dec2), enc1], dim=1),
43            t)
44
45        return self.final(dec1)
```

(a) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 11?

- A. `self.xatt = MyCrossAttention(img_channels=16, emb_dim=dim_txt_emb, key_dim=16, val_dim=16, out_dim=16, num_heads=4)`
- B. `self.xatt = MyCrossAttention(img_channels=16, emb_dim=dim_txt_emb, key_dim=16, val_dim=16, out_dim=8, num_heads=4)`

- C. `self.xatt = MyCrossAttention(img_channels=8, emb_dim=dim.txt_emb, key_dim=16, val_dim=16, out_dim=16, num_heads=4)`
- D. `self.xatt = MyCrossAttention(img_channels=8, emb_dim=dim.txt_emb, key_dim=16, val_dim=16, out_dim=8, num_heads=4)`

(b) (1 point) What is the correct code for Line 14?

- A. `self.dec2 = ConvBlock(in_channels=16, out_channels=16)`
- B. `self.dec2 = ConvBlock(in_channels=8, out_channels=16)`
- C. `self.dec2 = ConvBlock(in_channels=16, out_channels=8)`
- D. `self.dec2 = ConvBlock(in_channels=8, out_channels=8)`

7. Stable Diffusion Sudoku

Complete a part of the architecture of stable diffusion that was intentionally left out.

Figure 2: Stable Diffusion Mechanism

- (a) (1 point) Which component is covered by Γ ?
 - A. A self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A VAE encoder
 - C. A VAE decoder
 - D. A cross-attention module
 - E. A text embedding
- (b) (1 point) Which component is covered by Δ ?
 - A. A self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A VAE encoder
 - C. A VAE decoder

- D. A cross-attention module
 - E. A text embedding
- (c) (1 point) Which component is covered by β ?
- A. A self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A VAE encoder
 - C. A VAE decoder
 - D. A cross-attention module
 - E. A text embedding
- (d) (1 point) Which component is covered by α ?
- A. A self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A VAE encoder
 - C. A VAE decoder
 - D. A cross-attention module
 - E. A text embedding

8. **Vision Transformer Sudoku**

Below is a diagram of the vision transformer architecture.

Figure 3: The Vision transformer architecture

- (a) (1 point) Which component is covered by Γ ?
- A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A normalization layer.
 - D. A MLP.
 - E. A linear projection.

- (b) (1 point) Which component is covered by Δ ?
- A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A normalization layer.
 - D. A MLP.
 - E. A linear projection.
- (c) (1 point) Which component is covered by Ω ?
- A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A normalization layer.
 - D. A MLP.
 - E. A linear projection.
- (d) (1 point) Which component is covered by β ?
- A. A multi-headed self-attention mechanism.
 - B. A multi-headed masked self-attention mechanism.
 - C. A Normalization Layer.
 - D. A MLP.
 - E. A linear projection.

9. (1 point) **Diffusion models for bitstrings**

We want to create a diffusion process for bitstrings for short binary executables that result from compiling short programs in a specific programming language. How can we implement one step of the forward diffusion process?

- A. Pick two bits in the string at random and swap them.
- B. Randomly pick a subset of bits in the string and flip them.
- C. Randomly pick a subset of bits and set them to 0.
- D. Randomly pick two disjoint substrings and swap them.

10. (1 point) **Reverse Diffusion**

How would you implement one step of the reverse diffusion process? You may assume that the input is a time step and a bitstring.

- A. Randomly pick a subset of bits in the string and flip them.
- B. Randomly swap two disjoint substrings.
- C. Predict the changes done to that bitstring in the previous time step and revert them.
- D. Randomly pick a subset of bits and decide if they were affected by the forward step at the given time step.